

FIBRES' SURFACE MAPPING BY SOLVENT ADSORPTION METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Inverse Gas Chromatography (IGC) has proved to be a suitable tool to study solid surfaces and their interaction capability. The solutes are *retained* in their way through the chromatographic column accordingly to their particular interaction with the stationary phase, which depends on the surface groups in the stationary phase and the solute nature. The retention volume, V_R is related to the free energy of adsorption and many thermodynamic parameters can be obtained from the experimental data.

Surface interactivity of fibers and fillers is of key importance in composite materials, particularly in CMCs. A new approach is proposed in this work, the main achievement being to bring acid-base characterisation of the surfaces to the same energetic scale than that of the London component of the free surface energy measured by the interaction of n-alkanes with the surface.

Traditionally, the main *reference set of probes* used in IGC at infinite dilution is the n-alkane series (R-H). The free energy of adsorption of the members of this series provides a significant value, *the free energy of adsorption of the CH₂ group*.

In this paper other homologous series are proposed as probes to obtain outstanding information of the surface characteristics, particularly the presence or not of potential hydrogen-bond sites. For this purpose n-alcohol series (R-OH), used as probes, can provide valuable information like *the free energy of adsorption of the OH group* with the surface that is clearly related to the acid-basic character of the surface.

In this paper we show a work carried out on different solid surfaces: polyethylene, clean glass fibre, sized glass fibre and carbon fibre where these magnitudes can be accurately evaluated and which allow to distinguish clearly different surfaces.

A new methodology is proposed which allows an *energetic surface mapping*.

The two homologous series here used as probes are n-alkanes (R-H) and n-alcohols (R-OH), as well as the widely acid-base solvent probes.

KEYWORDS: Surface Free Energy, Inverse Gas Chromatography, n-alkane series, n-alcohol series, surface mapping.

INTRODUCTION

Reinforcing fibres, while able to carry only tensile load when in the form of non-impregnated strands, contribute most of the tensile, compressive, flexural and shear stiffness and strength of FRP laminates. The remarkable synergistic relationship between resin and reinforcement is highly dependent on the good adhesion at the interface between the fibre and the matrix. Reinforcement of marine FRP laminates is provided almost universally by glass fibres, especially E-glass fibres. Aircraft structures are mostly built with carbon fibre reinforced polymers. The deep knowledge of surface activity of commercial fibres will contribute to improve the choice of the manufacturing process parameters.

Gas Chromatography is an easy technique of separation and/or identification of solutes in a mixture, based on the fact that, each solute has a *particular* interaction with the stationary phase, and therefore, the different solutes travel through the column, carried by an inert gas, at different rates. The solutes

come out of the column separately and the retention volume, V_R , of each solute, depends on different parameters, among others, the nature of the stationary phase and the nature of the solute.

IGC takes advantage of this fact, by using a series of solutes (probes), of well known physicochemical characteristics. Introducing them into the column, and measuring their V_R , valuable information of the nature of the column can be obtained, being in this case the column material to be investigated.

Injecting a minimum vapour amount of solutes, in the limit of FID detector sensitivity, allows assuming that no solute-solute interactions take place, only solid-solute interactions occur. In these conditions, Henry's law can be applied and the proportion of adsorbed solute, and therefore the retention volume V_R , is practically independent of the probe concentration.¹⁻²

The retention volume (V_R) of a solute is related to standard variation of the free energy of adsorption according to

$$-\Delta G_A = R T \ln V_R + C \quad (1)$$

where C is a constant that depends on the reference state³, R is the gas constant and T is the column temperature in °K

According to Fowkes⁴, the solid surface is a set of different accessible active sites of different nature and heterogeneous character. The surface energy, γ_s , is the sum of the free energy of all of those active sites. Generally, γ_s can be split in two components

$$\gamma_s = \gamma_s^d + \gamma_s^{sp} \quad (2)$$

where γ_s^d , or the London component of the free energy, is the sum of the free energy of those active sites non-polar, that can only interact with in-coming molecules, with dispersive interactions, and γ_s^{sp} , or the Specific component of the free energy, is the sum of surface free energy, of all other specific active sites of polar nature, with different character and intensity.

Van der Waals attractions are widely accepted to be three main types⁵:

- a) Keesom Interactions (dipole-dipole)
- b) Debye Interactions (dipole-induced dipole)
- c) London Dispersion (induced dipole-induced dipole)

When injecting n-alkane in a column X, we obtain ΔG_{CH_2} (free energy of adsorption of a methylene group) from the slope of the line obtained when plotting ΔG_A , versus number of carbon atoms. This work of adhesion lacks of Keesom type interactions but on heterogeneous surfaces, it encloses also the interaction of the methylene group with polar sites on the surface, so the following expression is traditionally used

$$W_{aCH_2} = W_{aCH_2 \text{ London}} = 2 (\gamma_{CH_2}^d * \gamma_X^d)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

according to Fowkes's expression⁶, taking for $\gamma_{CH_2}^d$ the surface energy of members of the n-alkane series⁷, or that of polyethylene. Therefore the value γ_X^d can be calculated.

This value however, encloses both types of interactions, London and Debye, when n-alkanes are retained by the solid surface. Up to date no method has been described to distinguish in the γ_X^d calculated value, the fraction of purely unspecific sites and that fraction which is originated by the Debye interaction of polar sites with n-alkanes. How to split these two terms of the London component is the main object of this work.

In this paper a method is proposed to obtain a specific/unspecific fractional distribution of the surface sites, and also an energetic distribution.

The study of the interaction of the series of n-alcohols can provide a good evidence of the presence or absence of potential hydrogen-bridge formers among the basic sites of the surface.

One of the problems found in the calculation of the specific components of surfaces described in the literature has the origin in the energy units used for the work of adsorption of the polar probes, their donor and acceptor numbers, and therefore the value of K_a and K_b calculated.

TRADITIONAL CALCULATION OF K_a AND K_b OF A SURFACE THROUGH INJECTION OF POLAR PROBES

All methods described in the literature rely on the same philosophy. The free energy of adhesion is plotted versus a *chosen property* of the probes, which is likely to be in close relation with the *dispersive potential interactivity* of the molecule. The series of n-alkanes are included in this plot, which show a linear relation between the chosen property and the free energy of adhesion. The key point is to accept that, for a given polar probe, with a given value in the chosen characteristic, its dispersive work of interaction with the solid stationary phase, is the same, that the interaction of the hypothetical n-alkane with the same value in the chosen property. Among the chosen properties proposed by different authors are: $\log P^0$ ⁸, $a(\gamma_L^d)^{1/29}$, boiling temperatures T_b ¹⁰, molecular refraction P_D ¹¹, polarizability function¹², a new topology index, χ_T , is defined for this application¹³. We proposed a method¹⁴ in the same line, where the chosen property was the Kóvats index of the probe on a non-polar column like polyethylene. K_a and K_b were calculated by plotting I_{sp}/AN of each polar probe, versus DN/AN . The slope being $K_{a,s}$, and $K_{b,s}$ the intercept, assuming the equation

$$I_{sp} = K_{a,s} * DN_{probe} + K_{b,s} * AN_{probe} \quad (4)$$

We think that in most methods, too much free energy of adsorption is subtracted from the total interaction to find the specific fraction. With exception of J.B. Donnet et al.¹³, Vidal et al.¹⁵, and E. Brendlé et al.¹⁴ approaches, all properties are greatly conditioned by, not only dispersive interactions between polar probes molecules but by also by molecule-molecule interactions of polar character.

Other important drawback of this methodology is that, although in principle DN/AN are meaningful figures provided that donor and acceptor numbers are normalised in the same scale, *Isp energy values are in a totally different scale than AN or DN values*. The consequence is that the plot of I_{sp}/AN versus DN/AN will produce K_a and K_b data in *arbitrary energy units* which only have a limited comparative value.

In this paper we propose new AN and DN numbers in *carbon index scales, which is the same scale used to measure W_a of probes*.

EXPERIMENTAL

The instrument used is a Perkin Elmer Autosystem. The detector is flame ionisation (FID) in the highest sensitive range, in the limit of detection. The amount of probes injected is 0.01 to 50 μ l of gas, taken from the headspace of the vessels, to be sure of working at infinite dilution. The carrier gas is helium and the flow rates are in the range of 3 to 30 ml/min for each solid stationary phase studied.

Dead retention time, t_M , is calculated by mathematical fitting of expression

$$(t_E - A) = \exp(B + Cn) \quad (5)$$

Therefore for $n = 0$,

$$t_M = A + \exp B \quad (6)$$

which would be the retention time of an hypothetical n-alkane with 0 number of carbon atoms. The retention time of each member of the series of n- alkanes is

$$t_{Ri} = t_{Ei} - t_M \quad (7)$$

The fibres studied are

E-Glass fibre available in the laboratory with polyester sizing, and this same fibre solvent extracted.

Non-sized AS4 carbon fibre of Hexcel Composites.

The reference material is ground polyethylene (1- 5 μm diameter grain size) .

All materials were introduced in Teflon tubing of 1/4" or 1/8" outer diameter, V_R are *adjusted retention volumes*, calculated through

$$V_R = F_a (T_r/T_a) t_R \quad (8)$$

Where F_a is the carrier gas flow rate, measured at the column outlet at ambient pressure, and temperature (T_a), T_r is the reference temperature 25°C.

All probes injected for are HPLC quality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

POLYETHYLENE, PE, AS REFERENCE MATERIAL

The work of adsorption of any molecule can be expressed in different energy units. One of the most convenient is the before mentioned CH_2 index, (I_x) which is a slight modification of the well known Kòvats's index which value is independent of many variables like flow rate, column size, dead volume, % stationary phase, contact area, etc. I_x is only dependent on the probe characteristics, the characteristics of the stationary phase, and the temperature¹⁶.

By definition, the I_x value for n-alkane series *in any column and temperature* is n for $\text{C}_n \text{H}_{n+2}$

I_x value, for any other molecule, is the work of adsorption of that molecule divided by the work of adsorption of the methylene group *in the same column and temperature*.

The polar probes in PE have a work of adsorption that result in different retention volumes and therefore different retention indexes. We observe that these indexes, on polyethylene are almost non-temperature dependent, as can be shown in tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. I_x values of polar probes on PE

Molecule	60°	70°	80°	85°	90°	Average
Chloroform	6.11	6.18	6.21	6.20	6.21	6.18
Acetone	4.82	4.67	4.87	4.82	4.70	4.78
Ethyl acetate	5.83	5.81	5.85	5.78	5.74	5.80
Diethyl oxide	5.08	4.98	5.11	5.02	4.94	5.03
Tetrahydrofuran	6.23	6.26	6.30	6.27	6.31	6.27
Acetonitrile	4.85	4.64	4.90	4.86	4.70	4.79
Methylene chloride	5.51	5.52	5.58	5.53	5.47	5.53
2-Propyl alcohol	4.71	4.69	4.73	4.72	4.61	4.69

Table 2. Ix values of n-alcohols on PE

Molecule	60°	70°	80°	85°	90°	Average
Methanol	4.20	4.18	4.18	4.18	4.16	4.18
Ethanol	4.50	4.47	4.53	4.48	4.43	4.48
n-Propanol	5.28	5.33	5.36	5.34	5.26	5.31
n-Butyl alcohol	6.24	6.30	6.31	6.27	6.25	6.28
n-Pentyl alcohol	7.29	7.34	7.40	7.30	7.18	7.30
n-Hexyl alcohol	8.31	8.30	8.38	8.33	8.29	8.32
n-Heptyl alcohol	9.35	9.36	9.29	9.44	9.23	9.34
OH group	2.19	2.30	2.38	2.20	2.25	2.26

Ix of the hydroxyl group is obtained from the Ix of all members of the series of n-alcohols on PE. In fig.1 we see the Ix , average values, of ROH molecules on polyethylene versus number of CH₂ in the molecule. We obtain a line parallel to the n-alkane's where the *intercept* corresponds to Ix^{OH} on PE. This value is

$$I_{x}^{\text{OH}} \text{ on PE} = 2.26 \pm 0.08 \quad (9)$$

The interaction of the polar probes with polyethylene surface is a two-term magnitude: one accounting the London interaction of the unspecific part of the probe molecule, and the other accounting Debye interactions with the polar part of the probe molecule. The expression governing these interactions is not known, but we find experimentally an approximately linear correlation when plotting DN/AN* versus Ix/AN* of acetone, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, acetonitrile, 2-propyl alcohol, methanol and ethanol on polyethylene as shown in fig.2. The outliers are chloroform, methylene chloride and ethyl ether.

Fig.1. Carbon index of ROH homologous series on PE

Fig.2. Interaction of polar probes with PE

DN and AN numbers used here are those given by V. Gutmann¹⁷ F.L. Riddle Jr. and F.M. Fowkes¹⁸ From the linear equation found we recalculate DN/AN* values.

The linear relation shown in Fig.3 cannot be imputed to other than Debye interactions of polar probes with PE. Therefore we propose the following expression for these type of interactions

$$W_{\text{Debye}}(\text{probe L}) = \gamma_{\text{PE}} * \gamma_{\text{L}}^{\text{polar}} \quad (10)$$

and
$$\gamma_{\text{L}}^{\text{polar}} = (\text{AN} + \text{DN})_{\text{L}} \quad (11)$$

With the DN/AN corrected values, and expressions 10 and 11 we calculate new AN and DN_s for polar probes in index (on PE) energy units. These are shown in table 3

Table 3. New values for AN^x and DN^x of polar probes, in index energy units on PE

Probe	DN/AN ^{10,11}	DN/AN* corrected	AN (index on PE)	DN (index on PE)
Chloroform	0	3.81	2.57	9.79
Acetone	6.80	6.23	1.32	8.23
Ethyl acetate	11.40	12.41	0.87	10.74
Diethyl ether	13.71	11.53	0.80	9.25
Tetrahydrofuran	40.00	39.80	0.31	12.24
Acetonitrile	3.00	3.41	2.17	7.41
Methylene chloride	0	4.67	1.95	9.10
Methanol	1.58	1.30	3.64	4.72
Ethanol	1.94	1.57	3.49	5.48
OH		1.01	2.25	2.28

AN AND DN VALUES OF HYDROXYL GROUP, OH

In table 3 is also shown values for DN/AN and AN and DN numbers for the OH group. These are calculated in the following way.

Only three AN values of the series of n- alcohols are found in the literature: Methanol, Ethanol and Butanol. Methanol has enhanced OH polarity because of inductive effect of the CH₃- group. Ethanol shows the same effect but at a lesser extent because of the presence of the - CH₂ - link. Butanol shows practically no inductive effect on the OH polarity. In the homologous series ROH. This inductive

effect decays exponentially with increasing number of carbon atoms in the series. The dipolar character of OH group tends to a constant value which we take as the dipole character of OH group. Experimentally we obtain this magnitude by adjusting AN values found in the literature for the n-alcohols series, to an exponential decay curve with increasing carbon number. The value obtained is

$$AN(OH) = 8.7449 \text{ kcal/mol in Riddel-Fowkes scale}^{19} \quad (12)$$

Introducing this value in the line of fig 2 we obtain DN/AN (OH), consequently we calculate AN and DN values of OH group in *carbon index units, on PE*, once we measure this magnitude from the carbon index numbers of the ROH series an extrapolate to number of carbons $n = 0$. This is shown in fig 4 and the value of Wa OH in carbon index units on PE is found to be 2.2648

ACID AND BASIC CHARACTER OF SEVERAL SOLID MATERIALS.

The plot of Wa/AN of several polar probes versus DN/AN values gives a line comprising the sum of two contributions: a) a line of interactions of polar probes with the fraction of unspecific active sites of the solid, S , and b) a line of interactions of polar probes with basic-acid sites of the solid surface, S . We disclose these two terms by splitting the Wa (probe L) /AN

$$Wa_L \text{ total} /AN_L = Wa_L \text{ with specific sites of } S/AN_L + Wa_L \text{ with unspecific sites of } S/AN_L \quad (13)$$

where

$$Wa_L \text{ with specific sites of } S = (AN_L * Kb_S + DN_L * Ka_S) + \gamma_L^d * (Ka_S + Kb_S) \quad (14)$$

$$Wa_L \text{ with unspecific sites of } S = \gamma_S^d \text{ pure} (AN_L + DN_L) + 2 * (\gamma_S^d \text{ pure} * \gamma_L^d)^{1/2} \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma_S \text{ total} = Ka_S + Kb_S + \gamma_S^d \text{ pure} \quad (16)$$

In fig 3 we show the good correlations found in these plots on PE, non-sized carbon fibre, clean glass fibre and sized glass fibre. The four polar probes chosen are THF as basic, acetone and ethyl acetate as amphoteric and OH group as acid.

Fig.3. $Wa_L \text{ total} /AN_L$ versus $(DN/AN)_L$ in specific carbon index units

We could obtain Ka_S and Kb_S with eqs. 14 and 15 if we knew γ_L^d of each probe and $\gamma_S^d \text{ pure}$. As a first approximation we take $\gamma_S^d \text{ pure} \approx \gamma_S^d \text{ total}$, and $\gamma_L^d \approx 0$ for these four probes to split lines of fig.3 in two lines.

The application of expressions 13, 14 and 15 to the four chosen probes simultaneously (acetone, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, and the hydroxyl group), allows us by minimizing deviations of (Wa/AN)

experimental values from the calculated ones through the expressions 13, 14 and 15 to split the total line $(W_a/AN) = f(DN/AN)$ in two lines according with expression 13. The solution of this system provides us with optimum values for K_{a_s} and K_{b_s} , and therefore the fractional contribution of the non-specific sites to the total surface energy, which we give as an energetic map of the solid. As an example we show these splitting for the sized glass fibre in fig. 4.

Fig.4. Total, specific and unspecific lines in the case of sized glass fibre.

The slopes and intercepts obtained are used to evaluate the fractional energetic contributions to the total interaction, and the ratio slope/intercept of the *polar line*, as the (K_{a_s} / K_{b_s}) ratio.

The calculation of real K_{a_s} and K_{b_s} is done with $W_a(OH)$ exclusively, where $\gamma_L^d = 0$, and therefore the second term in both expressions 14 and 15 are 0. We can thus obtain the three components of expression 16.

SURFACE MAPPING OF SEVERAL MATERIALS

Calculated γ_s^d pure, K_a and K_b of solid X we can map the surface as shown in table 4.

Table 4. Surface map of several solid surfaces in kJ/mol. The total is $\gamma_X^d + K_{a_X} + K_{b_X}$

Material	Interaction energy fraction		London comp mJ/m2	Partial components in kJ/mol			kJ/mol
	%polar	%unspecific		Unspecific	Acid	Basic	
PE 70°C	0.01	0.99	40	1.4468	0.02	0.02	1.485
PE 80°C	-0.01	1.01	39	1.4063	-0.01	-0.01	1.388
Clean glass	0.79	0.21	33	1.1911	0.81	7.66	9.658
Sized glass	0.62	0.38	30	1.0788	0.28	4.21	5.568
Carbon fibre	0.61	0.39	61	2.2131	0.31	8.08	10.597

CONCLUSIONS

1. We can conclude from the results found that the *traditional total London component* of the surface is mainly an indication of the *concentration of active sites* giving no information of their energetic activity.
2. We propose new values of AN and DN for polar probes taking polyethylene as reference material and expressed in carbon number indexes.
3. We propose a method to evaluate AN number and DN number of hydroxyl group through the interaction of the n-alcohols with polyethylene.

4. We propose to use the work of adsorption of the hydroxyl group together with other three polar molecules to calculate unspecific, acid and basic components of the free surface energy of solids in the same energy units
5. We show, using this methodology an approximate surface map of the surface of polyethylene, clean glass fibre, sized glass fibre and carbon fibre.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to express their gratitude to E.A. Romero Arias for her laboratory work. Also to Hexcel Composites for providing with material.

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